

Chelating Ion-Exchangers Containing Thiosalicylamide as Functional Group for Separation of Platinum

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Chelating ion-exchangers containing thiosalicylamide as functional group sorb Pt^{II} and Pt^{IV} . The preparation and properties of four such resins with different matrices are studied and the resin derived from polystyrene matrix crosslinked with 4% divinylbenzene is found to be the most effective for the separation and concentration of traces of platinum ions in aqueous solutions. Pt^{II} has been quantitatively separated from a number of commonly associated metal ions, e.g. Ru^{III} , Rh^{III} , Os^{VIII} and Ir^{III} by the use of the chelating resins.

THIOSALICYLAMIDE, (TSA), has shown selective action towards the platinum metal ions and forms strong chelates. Its incorporation in the resin matrices should, therefore, be of much practical interest in the separation and concentration of these metals. In the present work, four chelating resins incorporating TSA as the functional group have been prepared and their analytical properties investigated. Complying with the expectation Pt^{II} and Pt^{IV} are strongly sorbed by these chelating resins from hydrochloric acid as well as from acetate media. Pt^{IV} , however, is partially reduced by the resins in the acid solution and the reduction is facilitated with the decrease in acidity. Again, unlike Pt^{II} , the retained Pt^{IV} cannot be desorbed by any suitable eluent.

Experimental

Preparation of resins: Copolymerization of 0.2 mol *o*-nitrophenol (Resin I)/*p*-nitrophenol (Resin II) with 0.05 mol phenol and 0.5 mol formaldehyde in presence of 5 ml hydrochloric acid was carried out at 70°. The solid mass formed was further crosslinked with paraformaldehyde at 130°. The nitropolymer produced, was reduced to aminopolymer, which was subsequently diazotised and coupled with 0.2 mol TSA in 10% Na_2CO_3 solution.

The starting materials for resins III and IV were polystyrene-4% DVB copolymer and polystyrene-8% DVB copolymer, respectively. The nitration¹ and reduction of the copolymers were carried out and finally coupled with TSA, as given above. The resulting chelating resins were Soxhleted with ethylalcohol, washed with *M* HCl and finally with deionized water.

Characterization of resins: The exchange capacities of the resins were measured in HCl medium (0.1-4.4 *M*) and also in the acetate buffer solution (pH 1.0-6.0) using standard platinum chloride solution (1.90 mg ml⁻¹). Equilibration rates of the resins

for Pt^{II} and Pt^{IV} at the corresponding optimal acidities were also determined. The sorbed Pt^{II} ions were eluted with 0.5% KCN solution. As no suitable eluent was found out to desorb Pt^{IV} , excess unabsorbed Pt^{IV} was estimated and the amount of Pt^{IV} retained by the resin was obtained by difference. All the determinations of the metal ions were carried out with A.A.S.

Water regains of the resins were determined, after drying them at 100° for 48 h.

Estimation of nitrogen, sulphur and amino groups: Nitrogen contents of the nitro, amino and the final product were determined. Sulphur was estimated by barium sulphate method. Amino contents of the aminated copolymers were determined by non-aqueous titrimetry².

Column separation: A 50 cm glass column (1.1 cm i.d.) was packed with 5 g resin previously soaked in HCl. The effective bed volume was 7.5 ml. A solution (50 ml) containing a known amount of Pt^{II} and a diverse ion in *M* HCl, was passed through the resin column, preconditioned with *M* HCl. The resin bed was washed with *M* HCl. Pt^{II} was then eluted with 30 ml 0.5% KCN solution at flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

All the resins have shown almost similar ability to sorb Pt^{II} and Pt^{IV} ions over a wide range of acidity. Both Pt^{II} and Pt^{IV} exhibit two maximum capacities. It has been found that with the decrease in acidity, the exchange capacity of the resins increases and reach a maximum at about 0.75 to 0.98 *M* acidity with respect to HCl, and then decreases. The exchange capacity again increases showing the maxima at pH 4.37 to 4.6. Among the prepared resins, the resin IV has shown maximum capacity for Pt^{II} (0.71 mmol g⁻¹ of dry resin at 0.82 *M* HCl and 0.98 mmol at pH 4.38), and for Pt^{IV} (0.68 mmol

g^{-1} of dry resin at 0.80 M HCl, and 0.98 mmol at pH 4.38). The times for 50% sorption of the resin IV for Pt^{2+} have been found to be lower at 0.82 M HCl (40 min) than at pH 4.38 (55 min). The greater equilibration rate of resin IV can be explained in terms of its macroporosity and maximum swelling property. (The water-regain values of resin I, II, III and IV are 0.60, 0.48, 0.42 and 1.18 g water/g resin, respectively). All the prepared resins exhibit reducing property which increases with decrease in the acidity. Pt^{2+} is partially reduced to Pt^{1+} before its sorption with the resin.

Different eluents have been tried to desorb the retained Pt^{2+} from the resin IV. Solutions of disodium salt of EDTA, potassium sodium tartrate, sodium citrate, orthophosphoric acid and M HCl failed to elute any Pt^{2+} ions. 20% elution can, however, be effected with 12 M HCl, 7% with 2% thiourea solution, and 30% with 2% stannous chloride solution. However, 0.5% KCN solution can elute the sorbed Pt^{2+} quantitatively.

The nitrogen content of the nitropolymer of resin IV is found to be 8.4%, and the amino derivative contains 9.63% total nitrogen and 6.75% amino nitrogen. The chelating resin, on analysis, gives 10.13% total nitrogen and 6.09% sulphur. Therefore, the dry resin IV contains 1.89 mmol of ligand nitrogen. However, the maximum exchange capacity of resin IV for Pt^{2+} is found to be 0.98 mmol g^{-1} of dry resin. Steric factor is probably responsible for this low value.

Separation of platinum(II) ions with the resin IV : Resin IV has been chosen for column operation due

to its better equilibration rate and higher exchange capacity. The retention and elution characteristics of a large number of co-ions have been examined. Zn^{2+} , As^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Zr^{4+} , Ti^{4+} , Ga^{3+} , In^{3+} , Tl^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Th^{4+} , U^{6+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Rh^{3+} and Ir^{3+} are not sorbed by the resin IV from any acidic solution. Cd^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Se^{2+} and Te^{2+} are not sorbed by the resin from solutions in M HCl. It is thus possible to separate quantitatively Pt^{2+} (5.7 mg or 11.4 μg) from mixtures containing 170 mg or 300 μg , respectively of each of the above mentioned metal ions in M HCl solution by circulating the solutions through the resin. The sorbed Pt^{2+} is eluted with four bed volumes of 0.5% KCN solution. Fe^{3+} is sorbed (0.027 mmol g^{-1} dry resin at M HCl) by the resin, which can be selectively eluted with (1 : 5) H_3PO_4 . Ru^{3+} , V^{5+} and Os^{7+} , when previously reduced by SO_2 , are not sorbed at M HCl. Mo^{6+} , when reduced by SO_2 , is however, slightly sorbed (0.014 mmol g^{-1} dry resin at M HCl). The sorbed molybdenum ions can be selectively eluted with four bed volumes of 5% potassium sodium tartrate solution. Macro or micro amounts of Pt^{2+} have been effectively separated from Fe^{3+} , Ru^{3+} , V^{5+} , Os^{7+} and Mo^{6+} by the use of the aforesaid resin. The interferences of Au^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Hg^{2+} and Pd^{2+} , however, cannot be avoided.

References

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